

Possible Antituberculous Compounds. Part XI. Preparation of α - and β -Naphthylamidines

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To establish the relationship between basic strength and antituberculous activity, six new α -naphthylamidines and seven new β -naphthylamidines have been prepared.

A survey of the literature reveals that only *N*-1-naphthylbenzamidine has been tested and found to possess antitubercular activity greater than that of the parent α -naphthylamine¹.

In the present communication we have tried to increase the basic strength of α - and β -naphthylamines by synthesising a number of amidines (alkyl and aryl) by the well-known method of Oxley and Short².

The α - and β -naphthylamines were converted into the corresponding naphthylammoniumbenzenesulphonates by the method of Bauer and Cymerman³ and as adopted by us earlier⁴.

These benzenesulphonates were fused at 180-230° with an excess of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-, tolu-, α - and β -naphtho-, aceto-, and valero-nitriles respectively and the corresponding amidine benzenesulphonates isolated. The free amidines were obtained by basification of these sulphonates with 5*N*-NaOH solution. These were subsequently recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b. p. 60-80°).

The steps involved in the synthesis are:

[R=tolyl (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-), C₁₀H₇ (α & β), CH₃-, CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂-]

The antitubercular activity will be reported later on.

1. Oxley and Peak, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 485.
2. *Ibid.*, 1946, 147.
3. *Ibid.*, 1950, 1826.
4. Misra *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 695; 1959, 36, 270.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Naphthyl Ammoniumbenzenesulphonate (A).— α -Naphthylamine (10 g.) in dry ether (200 ml) was stirred mechanically and benzenesulphonic acid (10.5 g.), dissolved in absolute methanol (15 ml), was added to it dropwise. The benzenesulphonate separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from hot water as brown leaflets, m.p. 220-22°, yield 12 g. (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3NS$ requires N, 4.65%).

β -Naphthyl ammoniumbenzenesulphonate (B) was prepared in an analogous manner from β -naphthylamine (10 g.); m.p. 230°, yield 12.5 g. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3NS$ requires N, 4.65%).

α -Naphthylamidines.—The compound (A) (1 g.) was mixed with the corresponding nitriles (1 g.) in a 100 ml r. b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube and the mixture was heated at 180-230° (external bath temperature) for 4 to 5 hours. The contents were cooled and triturated with ether when the subsequent amidine benzenesulphonates were obtained. The above sulphonates were stirred with 5N-NaOH (50 ml). The amidines so obtained were filtered and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether.

β -Naphthylamidines were obtained in the similar manner from the compound (B) and nitrile, 1g. each.

TABLE I

No.	R.	M.P.	Formula.	Yield.	Appearance.
1	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	40%	Black
2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160-62°	"	45	Dark brown
3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	110°	"	50	Brown
4	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	170°	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	60	"
5	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	60-70°	"	80	Dark grey
6	Me	200°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S	20	Light brown
7	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃	"	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	30	" "

TABLE II

*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	185°	20%	Dark brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂	10.0	10.77
2	> 262°	30	Brown	"	11.0	10.77
3	> 235°	40	Light brown	"	10.4	10.77
4	240°	50	Dark brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	9.9	9.46
5	150-52°	70	Light brown	"	10.0	9.46
**6	> 255°	14	Do	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂	14.9	15.21
7	185°	20	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂	11.8	12.38

*R of amidine, same as in Table I.

**This amidine was also prepared (Berntsen, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 1758) by direct heating of α -naphthylamine HCl and acetonitrile.

TABLE III
 β -C₁₀H₇NHC: NHC₆H₅HSO₃R

*No.	M.P.	Formula.	Yield.	Appearance.
1	170°	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ N ₂ S	80%	Dark brown
2	160°	"	70	Brown,
3	155°	"	90	Light brown
4	182°	C ₂₇ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	90	Brown
5	185°	"	80	Dark brown.
6	110°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	30	Grey
7	> 235°	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	20	Brown

R, same as in Table I.

TABLE IV
 β -C₁₀H₇NHC: NHR.

No.	Amidine.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	133°	30%	Dark brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂	10.5	10.77
2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	225°	50	Brown	"	11.0	10.77
3	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135°	90	Grey	"	10.1	10.77
4	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	165°	80	Do	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	6.9	9.46
5	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	205°	90	Brown	"	9.0	9.46
6	Me	120°	6	Dark brown	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂	14.9	15.21
7	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃	121°	10	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₂	11.9	12.38

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